

Calculation of photon fluxes for different spectral types

L Lindegren, 8 Dec 1997 (SAG_LL_011.txt)

Assumptions as in SAG_LL_007.txt (QE, stellar fluxes).

Table 1. Flux (Hz) versus wavelength range for V = 15, A_V = 0.
Pupil area = 0.5655 m² (2*0.6 m diam), optical transmittance = 0.8.
The numbers below the spectral types are the colour indices V-Ic.

nm	B0Ib -0.33	A0V -0.02	G2V +0.70	K3III +1.33	M7III +4.54	M8V +3.14
300-	19329.61	16492.60	17824.19	22371.70	286994.6	71882.77
400-	14375.10	14752.81	16974.98	22223.97	286770.8	71767.80
500-	8219.657	9335.855	13459.00	20050.82	285431.5	70307.30
550-	6083.346	7219.126	11453.26	18198.86	283639.7	68377.25
600-	4388.593	5433.658	9365.843	15717.13	281186.7	65997.62
650-	3061.969	3949.784	7332.523	12933.69	276091.2	62462.94
700-	2039.032	2749.365	5377.947	9938.980	264746.4	57192.61
750-	1283.630	1767.221	3665.329	7130.107	239339.4	47521.34
800-	792.9379	1080.339	2313.169	4690.798	204481.7	36070.39
850-	436.7568	624.8048	1355.174	2894.036	147852.0	23443.19
900-	205.9570	302.9934	662.4764	1466.161	96911.74	13109.16
950-	66.19971	104.1629	231.5357	553.7742	43136.56	5198.325
300-400	4954.429	1739.734	849.1769	147.7078	223.8409	114.9823
400-550	8291.704	7533.625	5521.679	4025.054	3130.579	3390.458
550-700	4044.281	4469.726	6075.249	8259.775	18892.72	11184.42
700-850	1602.266	2124.547	4022.745	7044.898	116893.5	33749.09
850-	436.7568	624.8048	1355.174	2894.036	147852.0	23443.19

Table 2. Flux (Hz) versus wavelength range for V = 15, A_V = 5.
Pupil area = 0.5655 m² (2*0.6 m diam), optical transmittance = 0.8.
The numbers below the spectral types are the colour indices V-Ic.

nm	B0Ib +1.65	A0V +1.94	G2V +2.62	K3III +3.19	M7III +6.37	M8V +5.01
300-	27397.93	32679.89	52667.32	85578.37	2098325.	443572.6
400-	26942.47	32494.62	52587.74	85565.14	2098303.	443561.8
500-	25020.70	30807.89	51467.48	84854.30	2097956.	443079.0
550-	23169.96	29001.14	49824.50	83408.65	2096664.	441581.2
600-	20587.76	26321.06	46845.08	80067.86	2093677.	438491.2
650-	17582.53	23010.86	42529.41	74519.72	2084168.	431474.6
700-	14231.23	19123.75	36535.97	65906.00	2053591.	416829.1
750-	10789.78	14719.42	29248.66	54692.26	1957279.	378361.2
800-	7799.872	10611.05	21576.55	41735.30	1790931.	319212.8
850-	4988.681	7073.585	14535.93	29358.25	1439250.	234837.6
900-	2694.948	3924.116	8122.931	16949.64	1032180.	147702.4
950-	991.3293	1539.222	3231.552	7270.625	516898.2	66236.65
300-400	455.4250	185.2106	79.54877	13.16425	21.29927	10.57156
400-550	3772.472	3493.418	2763.190	2156.487	1639.522	1980.811
550-700	8938.605	9877.271	13288.32	17502.38	43070.23	24750.79
700-850	9242.457	12050.05	21999.82	36547.35	614333.9	181989.3
850-	4988.681	7073.585	14535.93	29358.25	1439250.	234837.6